

THE STUDY OF NEW AGE MEDIA ADVERTISING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RICH SITE SUMMARY (RSS)

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Abstract:

Advertising has always been an integral part of business. Companies in recent times are witnessing an innovation in new channels of media such as google, twitter, facebook, youtube etc which enables customers to pay an active role in marketing communication. Consumers of today can be reached anywhere and anytime. The new media provides an ample opportunity for revamp in business models and corporate strategies. The new media impacts the relationships with customers and helps in creating and managing the relationships. There creates huge challenges for academicians and practitioners to understand the consumer behaviour and to understand the interactions of the consumer with new age media and the measurement of the outcome of these interactions. Consumers rely heavily on online reviews when they make purchasing choices in today's globalised setup industry. Consumers share their positive and negative experiences. So they become more like an influencers to other consumers. One of the trends that is getting popular is Rich Site summary (RSS). Rich Site summary uses a category of standard web feed formats which are used to publish frequently updated information, blog information, news updates, audio and video. The RSS feed organizes the world into a series of constantly updated and clickable and interesting bits of information. It is a relatively new concept which is still unutilized. It can be seamlessly integrated into real time. The RSS feeds now prevails online subject intake. It's available everywhere from the news that is read by the consumer on his mobile devices to the interaction that happens in social network. The advertisements are also integrated into these platforms so that the companies are visible to the consumers where they are available. The basic objective of this paper "The study of new age media in advertising with special reference to Rich Site Summary (RSS)" aims at understanding the contribution of RSS in the world of digital advertising. A case study approach will be adopted to study this concept for better understanding and implications. The research uses secondary data for the collection of data. Conclusions, based on the outcome, hereby obtained were drawn and decisions were taken about the said objectives. The primary purpose of this paper is to stimulate further discussion amongst marketers and to be used in dialogue with stakeholders.

Index Terms: Rich Site Summary Feeds, Digital Advertising, Consumer & Companies

1. Introduction:

Web syndication is a form of syndication in which a section of a website is made available for other sites to use. Most commonly, web syndication refers to making web feeds available to other websites, using "web feed" programs, such as RSS (Really Simple Syndication) and Atom, which provide the means to deliver content over the web. Web feed programs can check the content for changes and updates in order to provide users with a summary of the website's recently added content (e.g. updates, latest news, most recent blog or forum posts). A technology that distributes a website's information (whatever it might be, e.g.. articles, special offers, product reviews, resource announcements) by syndicating it across the Internet. RSS is the plumbing that connects users to the content they like and has provided the freedom to aggregate content anywhere on any device. This streaming of content, or life streaming, is a compilation of one's interests aggregated in a central experience preferred by the consumer. The outcome in today's distributed media world is fragmentation of both the content and the consumer. Stitching together and making sense of the user behaviour with the content off the site poses new challenges. Brands successfully leveraging RSS and distributed media understand the power of the medium. They realize RSS is about people not the amount of page views. It is not a tonnage buy but micro-targeting.

- ✓ Create great content that is relevant to the user you are trying to attract.
- ✓ Virally-enable the content for easy sharing
- ✓ Create the content so it is digestible in micro-chunks
- ✓ Determine the right amount of content flow to keep users engaged
- ✓ Consider the whole experience when evaluating success (vs. just clicks)

RSS feeds will encourage brands to create a life stream (brand stream) of their own. A brand is a living, breathing organism. A brand is about the people who make up that brand. So therefore, a brand has life. Content in a brands life might include press releases, product reviews, blog postings, pictures of the company picnic, whitepapers mostly likely all the things they already have but not centralized. RSS advertising was started by

Bill Flitter, CEO of Pheedo in 2003. The Company Pheedo are a major company that provides in-feed RSS advertising services for many publishers. Cisco is leveraging brand streaming as a lead nurturing technique. They created a feed of content that includes video, press releases, customer stories and product updates as a way to connect with their potential customers.

2. The Way RSS Works:

To start using RSS for free — all you need is a valid Internet connection and a program called an RSS aggregator. Typically, aggregators come in two varieties; they can be Web-based or desktop-based. There are also a number of programs and add-ons that provide RSS functionality to email clients and Web browsers. Once installed a feed reader, RSS can get started. There are hundreds of aggregators out there, with all kinds of different interfaces and useful features, so finding one you like is just a matter of experimentation. Google shut down its coveted Reader service in July 2013, but now a number of new software options have come about since then that are more than capable of handling your subscriptions. The most popular of these options is given its ease-of-use, robust compatibility, and the mere fact that many sites feature an embedded shortcut button for utilizing it. Generally, if a site supports RSS subscriptions if it features an orange icon with a set of white lines running through it, similar to the image at right . You'll be hard pressed to find a site that doesn't support RSS these days, though, considering most sites offer an RSS button directly alongside buttons you click for Facebook and Twitter updates.

3. Benefits and Limitations of Syndication:

Some of the benefits of using web feeds for syndication include:

- ✓ It is a low cost and efficient way to deliver your content to subscribers, customers, and partners.
- ✓ Quick content indexing.
- ✓ Increased traffic to your website.
- ✓ Your website content is published on other websites.
- ✓ Increased market reach.

A potential limitation of syndication is that content authors can lose control over how their content is presented.

4. Marketing Effectiveness of RSS Feeds:

Advertisers who are truly taking advantage of the RSS architecture want to keep their success a secret. It is observed that engagement rates as high as 10%. Engagement is a compilation of the number of clicks on the content, word-of-mouth activity created, subscriptions to the content, and post subscription activity stitched together into a digestible metric. As the users taste for content consumption evolves so too does how marketers evaluate success. New standards of measurement are needed. Only measuring Click through Rate (CTR) tells a partial story. Marketers should ask questions like the recommendation of the user, the value for the user to recommend a product and the measurement of forwarding content to someone else. The companies' virally-enable all the content assets to increase the possibilities of sharing and report that activity back to the advertiser. They also provide the same analytic tools to advertisers that we provide publishers. This gives advertisers a detailed look into how their content is being consumed. Advertisers range from what you would expect, IT to consumer technology companies. However CPG companies, auto makers, and movie studios who target mothers and general consumers are taking full-advantage of the benefits of on-demand content tailored to the individual. The adoption rates of RSS feeds is high. Though it's still in niche category for advertising it's in the early stage of adoption and picking up quite fast. It is mostly suitable to tech-savvy audience. There is a 250% growth in the online traffic. 2008 onwards is the years of where RSS feeds became very popular. There is an expected 250% growth in the distribution traffic. 2008 was the year of syndication and aggregation. It is the year, where RSS realizes its inflection point. Advertising in RSS feeds will become a necessity as the feed becomes the main interaction point with a publisher. Most of the top consumer tech and news publishers observe more traffic in their feeds than on their websites. A study indicated 53% of online users are consuming RSS. That is faster growth than social networking and video consumption. Publishers are not the only ones who need to create feeds. Brands who want to participate in a user's life stream will need to create feeds to stay stop of mind with their consumers. Email marketing was before prior the RSS feeds. But the response rates drop and legal issues involved in it was making the marketers difficult to communicate with the consumers. So the necessity to get connected to consumers in better way was needed. This led to the idea of RSS feeds. Both sided benefits were derived out of this like brands received a communication channel and consumers had the control they desired. Advertising in RSS feeds is still considered new media. Rates have increased 28% in 12 months as media buyers have come to understand and appreciate the potential of reaching the content aggregators and broadcasters. Because RSS is a more personalized medium and therefore highly targeted, expect rates to be competitively priced and more in line with premium inventory rates.

5. Advertising in RSS Feeds:

As publishers have moved towards monetizing RSS feeds, their have been vibrant discussions as to whether advertisements in feeds are viable or whether they will drive subscribers away. At the end of the day while it appears that many are discussing the philosophical approaches to ads in RSS feeds few are taking the time to examine the options available for inserting advertisements in feeds. Ultimately the advertisements served

are going to determine the success of RSS as an advertising medium. The ads served must be related to the content contained in the feed. If the RSS feed contains quality content, the ads are relevant, and the volume of ads is in balance with the volume of content served, advertising in RSS feeds will succeed. Take a closer look at some of the ad serving options currently available for RSS feeds.

6. Review of Current Options Google AdSense for Feeds

Google's AdSense for Feeds offers contextually targeted advertisements, with a wide selection of advertisers. Google chooses not to divulge the percentage of revenue that is shared with the publisher, so it is difficult if not impossible to predict monthly revenue. The current Google AdSense system for feeds is tied to blogs and does not appear to be overly flexible.

7. Pheedo:

Pheedo displays categorized advertisements rather than contextual advertisements. The upside to this is that Pheedo's advertisements can be used in conjunction with Google AdSense or AdSense for feeds without violating Google's contract. Pheedo works with the publisher to serve advertisements from similar or related categories associated with the feeds contents. Pheedo's system allows for advanced ad filtering, giving publishers control over keyword ad filtering, specific ad filtering or url filtering. Pheedo's system also allows publishers to sell ads to existing advertisers whom they already have a relationship. The revenue split is 50% and feeds can be a sponsored flat rate advertisement or a pay-per-click advertisement, where the publisher is only paid if the advertisement is clicked.

Kanoodle for Feeds:

Kanoodles systems for providing advertisements for feeds is similar to Google's but they do not have the breadth of advertisers that Google boasts. Advertisements are served based on topics, not to keywords. Kanoodle shares 50% of the revenue generated from the advertisements with the publisher serving the ad.

8. Evaluating Options:

When evaluating feed ad serving solutions consider the following:

- ✓ **Ad Relevance:** In order to generate revenue from RSS advertisements or for an advertising campaign to succeed using RSS as a channel it is absolutely critical that the advertisements served in the feed contain related content, the more related the content the higher the likelihood that the advertisements will be of interest to the reader and clicked. Also the closer the content relates to the feeds theme the higher the likelihood the reader will have genuine interest in the product or service being advertised.
- ✓ **Ad Ratio:** Publishers need to retain control over the frequency of advertisements. Readers will become frustrated with feeds that are heavily laden with advertisements and genuine content. The advertiser is happy as they are reaching a targeted audience the publisher is happy because their advertisement is being clicked and generating revenue.
- ✓ **Clearly Denoted as Ads:** The debate over editorial control and advertisements rage on is generally considered proper net etiquette for publishers to clearly mark advertisements to distinguish them from editorial web content. When selecting a RSS advertising partner consider the context in which the advertisements are displayed. Does it blend with the feed or site, while still being clearly marked sponsored material? Or does the content blend so well that it appear as a product or service endorsement from the publisher? Credibility and reputation online matter, and the segregation of advertisements and ensuring they are properly denoted as such will go a long way to enhance credibility with readers. Clearly as RSS increases in popularity publishers are looking for ways to monetize their content. RSS in advertising is a logical step, and striking a balance between quality, consistent content and occasional related advertisements will lead to the success of advertising in RSS feeds. If the balance is not found, publishers may be forced to move to a subscription RSS feed model. RSS is an easy way to keep updated on the news that is of interest to you. Instead of having to go to websites to find out the latest news or articles, you can use RSS (Really Simple Syndication) to keep you posted with the latest website news and articles. RSS uses a feed reader or aggregator program to gather RSS Feeds. Whenever the consumer sees this icon he simply clicks or copies the URL of the feed to their preferred RSS reader to subscribe. They will then be updated with the latest news as it becomes available on the website

9. Types of Advertisements for RSS Feeds:

When the companies choose to put ads on your blog(s), there are a few options. The two most widely-used types of advertisements are traffic-based ads and pay-per-click ads. If the companies are using traffic-based ads, they are paid based on the number of page views the blog receives, not how many times readers click the ads. If the companies are using pay-per-click ads, it doesn't matter how many page views done, they are only paid if a reader clicks on the ad. If you choose to include ads in your RSS feeds, the options currently available are mostly context-based pay-per-click ads resembling the Google AdSense model. This is a list below of some of the companies that can help in monetising RSS feed:

- ✓ Google AdSense provides context-based ads. Since Google owns Feed burner, they can easily include Google AdSense inside the consumers feed if they are currently signed up with Feed burner. The

consumer just needs to log in to their Feed burner account, click the Monetize tab, and follow the directions.

- ✓ CrispAds offers context-based ads and will let the consumer choose what ads are included with their content.
- ✓ Feedvertsing uses text-link ads. The consumers have the option of approving or denying specific ads.
- ✓ Pheedo Inc. allows you to control the keyword filters and specific advertisements being shown in your feed.

10. Things to be Considered Before Including Ads in Your RSS Feed:

It's tempting for the companies to include ads within your feed(s) because it's a potential revenue stream. However, the companies are strongly encouraged to consider three things before they make the final decision:

- ✓ The ads are being served relevant to the companies blog content.
- ✓ The number of ads will appear within the feed. Readers don't like it when they can't find the content they're looking for because it's buried between ads. When ads take over the RSS feed or the blog, the focus of the blog might be lost. The readers might not be interested.
- ✓ The ads should be clearly marked so that readers don't confuse ads with blog content. Readers don't appreciate being duped. As a blogger, there is an obligation to make sure that content and ads are clearly separated and aren't confused.

Advertising on blogs is fairly common these days, but, all in all, RSS feed advertizing really is growing at a slow pace. The reasons could be

- ✓ a lack of advertising options within feeds,
- ✓ the fact that most blogs using RSS ads are making very little money
- ✓ the perception that it may be difficult to set up feeds to serve the ads, or
- ✓ bloggers simply don't consider RSS as another revenue stream.

Although most of the consumers read much of news from within the feed reader, they do click over to the actual site to read more thoroughly and comment. If the feeds are cluttered with ads, the consumers may opt to stop reading a blog completely. Otherwise ads would be distracting force for all consumers. Traditionally, RSS feeds are read through a feed reader or news aggregator. Lately, though, more and more people are asking for feeds via e-mail. Feed burner is free, allows you to manage multiple feeds, and it's easy to use. RSS is all about simplifying the way things are viewed and digest content on the Internet. Web pages are typically multimedia experiences, with multiple columns of images, text, and advertisements. An RSS feed of a page strips the information down to the bare essentials — usually the main text content, main images, or in the case of podcasts and video channels, the content itself. By reducing the desired content down to just what is really wanted, everyone can enjoy it on a larger number of platforms without worrying about compatibility or display issues. It also allows keeping track of when new content is posted without requiring refreshing the blog or podcast page every 10 minutes until something new appears.

11. Future of RSS Feeds:

RSS has gone through three macro stages.

- ✓ Awareness (2005) - what is it and why do the companies and consumers need it.
- ✓ Analysis (2006/07)- now that consumers and companies have it, how much of this can be used for the mutual benefit
- ✓ Monetization (2008 to present)- The need for creation of ROI and justifying the expenses

The 4th stage will be ROI Impact. Publishers/Brands are working today and realizing they need to put together a strategy around distributed media. They want to understand the full RSS ROI impact for their business. Over the next few years, the user experience will become more rich. RSS will be their main connection with the content they like. It will include social features and medium-specific advertising. Rich media ads will be redefined in RSS. Users can interact with the ad beyond just clicking on it and landing on the advertisers website. They can subscribe to the content, share it or save it for later. It delivers text, audio or video feeds. Really Simple Syndication (RSS) is an XML-based format for content distribution. Example: Adweek offers several RSS feeds for use in news readers and Web logs (blogs). These feeds include headlines, summaries and links back to Adweek.com for the full article. RSS feeds are free and Adweek.com currently uses RSS 2.0. The present RSS feeds is Web-based, so it's easy to simply point your smartphone, tablet, or computer to the site before logging in with your Google or Twitter account. The developers also offer an iOS, Android, and Kindle app, along with a number of desktop apps that that work with its API, so you can browse from anywhere without having to worry about juggling multiple feeds.

12. Conclusion:

RSS can be used for more than just combing news, music, and videos. Sites like Craigslist and eBay support RSS subscriptions to specific categories of services and items. In summary, RSS is a fantastic way to organize and consume the Web with increased efficiency and ease. If the consumers do most of your reading on the Web, a sturdy RSS reader is a must-have.

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